

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSOCIATION OF EPILEPSY WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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Abstract

The relationship between epilepsy and metabolic syndrome (MetS) has garnered increasing attention due to the overlapping prevalence of these conditions and their shared pathophysiological mechanisms. Epilepsy is one of the most common neurological disorders globally, with significant variation in incidence between high- and low-income countries. MetS, characterized by insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and central obesity, poses a substantial risk for cardiovascular diseases and diabetes. This study explores the potential associations between epilepsy and the components of MetS, such as obesity, hypertension, and hyperglycemia, and their contribution to the development of epilepsy. Inflammation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and altered neurotransmitter pathways are highlighted as key mechanisms underlying these associations. Additionally, the study examines the impact of antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) on metabolic profiles and the role of lifestyle factors in modulating both epilepsy and MetS outcomes. Understanding these interrelations may improve therapeutic strategies and patient outcomes, particularly in those affected by both epilepsy and MetS.

Keywords: epilepsy, metabolic syndrome, insulin resistance, obesity, hypertension, antiepileptic drugs, inflammation, mitochondrial dysfunction, hyperglycemia, cardiovascular risk.

Introduction

According to the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) definition of 2017 [6], an epileptic seizure is defined as a transient onset of specific signs and/or symptoms due to pathological excessive or synchronous activity of brain neurons (usually lasting up to 2 minutes). Epilepsy is diagnosed in one of three cases: ≥ 2 unprovoked or reflex seizures with an interval of >24 hours; 1 unprovoked or reflex seizure in a person with a risk of $\geq 60\%$ of occurrence of the next one within 10 years (criteria for this are potentially epileptogenic brain imaging findings and epileptiform activity on the EEG); epileptic syndrome.

Epileptic seizures are divided into those with focal (with and without impairment of consciousness), generalized and unknown onset. Seizures with focal onset: motor (automatism, atonic, clonic, epileptic spasms,

hyperkinetic, myoclonic, tonic), non-motor (autonomic, behavioral arrest, cognitive, emotional, sensory). Focal seizures can turn into bilateral tonic-clonic seizures. Seizures with generalized onset: motor (tonic-clonic, clonic, tonic, myoclonic, myoclonic-tonic-clonic, myoclonic-atonic, atonic, epileptic spasms), non-motor (absences) (typical, atypical, myoclonic, eyelid myoclonus). Seizures with unknown onset: motor (tonic-clonic, epileptic spasms), non-motor (behavioral arrest). They can also be unclassified [7].

Types of epilepsy: focal, generalized, combined, unclassified. The combination of specific features (clinical, EEG, imaging, triggers, genetic, age-dependent) also allows us to distinguish epileptic syndromes [6].

The chance that a person will have at least one epileptic seizure in their lifetime is 10%. Most of these people will not develop epilepsy, but it is one of the

most common neurological and psychiatric diseases affecting about 50 million (1-2%) people worldwide [1]. The global incidence of epilepsy in 1990-2016 ranged from 50.4 to 81.7 cases per 100,000 people per year [2]. The prevalence of epilepsy is likely to increase as more people survive serious head injuries, strokes, and intracranial infections, and live longer with primary and secondary brain tumors, thanks to modern medical advances [3]. There is a significant discrepancy in the prevalence and incidence of epilepsy in high- and low-income countries, with a significant prevalence in the latter: in developed countries, the prevalence of epilepsy is 5.8 per 1000 people (95% CI: 2.7-12.4), and in developing countries - 15.4 per 1000 people (95% CI: 4.8-49.6) [4]. It is believed that this discrepancy may be due to higher rates of parasitic infections (e.g., neurocysticercosis), higher incidence of head trauma, lower availability of treatment (in particular, anticonvulsants), and, to some extent, some genetic factors that are more common in developing countries. According to the WHO, almost 70% of patients with epilepsy could be free of seizures if they were diagnosed and treated correctly and in a timely manner [1]. There are 2 age peaks of epilepsy - 5-9 years and approximately 80 years. In addition, there is no difference in its prevalence by gender [5].

The metabolic syndrome (MetS) forms a cluster of metabolic disorders, including insulin resistance, atherogenic dyslipidemia, central obesity, and hypertension. If untreated, it is significantly associated with an increased risk of developing diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease, which are currently the leading cause of death in the world [8].

According to the American Heart Association (AHA) from 2009 [9], the diagnosis of MetS is established in the presence of ≥ 3 of the following criteria: central obesity (waist circumference for men >101.6 cm, for women >88.9 cm), abnormal blood glucose levels (elevated fasting levels >100 mg/dL) or being on treatment for elevated levels or having type 2 diabetes), high blood triglyceride levels (≥ 150 mg/dL or being treated for high levels), low HDL (<40 mg/dL for men and <50 mg/dL for women or being treated for low levels), high blood pressure (≥ 130 mm Hg SBP and/or ≥ 85 mm Hg DBP or being treated for hypertension). The collective term MetS also includes non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. These disorders occur in tandem, share common risk factors, and are associated with an increased risk of disability, malignancy, and premature death [10].

The US NHANES (National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey) 2011-18 study [11] estimated the overall prevalence of MetS and its components in the population from 2011 to 2018: the overall prevalence of MetS increased from 37.6% [95% CI: 34.0%-41.4%] in 2011-12 to 41.8% (95% CI: 38.1%-45.7%) in 2017-18 (P for trend = 0.028). Among the MetS components, the prevalence of elevated glucose increased from 48.9% (95% CI: 45.7%-52.5%) in 2011-12 to 64.7% (95% CI: 61.4%-67.9%) in 2017-18 (P for trend <0.001). The prevalence of MetS among participants with low education increased from 44.4% (95% CI:

38.8%-50.1%) in 2011-12 to 55.0% (95% CI: 50.8%-59.1%) in 2017-18 (P for trend = 0.01).

Etiology and Pathogenesis of Epilepsy

The etiologic factors for epilepsy are structural, genetic, infectious, metabolic, and immune. In addition, there are unknown factors in the development of epilepsy. Also, etiology can often fall into more than one category [6].

Structural etiology can be acquired, as in the case of stroke, trauma, or infection, but it can also be due to a genetic cause, such as tuberous sclerosis complex. In the case of structural abnormalities caused by genetic changes, it is the structural changes that are the main cause of epilepsy. Epilepsy is attributed to structural etiology if abnormalities are observed on neuroimaging, and the seizure semiology and EEG findings are consistent with onset in the same area as the abnormalities on neuroimaging [6].

Epilepsies of genetic etiology are those that result directly from a known or suspected genetic mutation, and epilepsy is the main symptom of this disorder. Genetic changes can include mutations, deletions, and copy number changes at the chromosome or gene level. Significant progress has been made in genetic testing, and more and more patients with genetic etiology are being identified. A genetic cause is found in 30-50% of infants with developmental encephalopathies and epileptic encephalopathies [12]. In addition, genetic testing is a more cost-effective diagnostic method for some epileptic syndromes with negative neuroimaging findings [13]. In addition, epilepsy can be classified as genetic in nature in the absence of a definitive genetic mutation that causes it in cases where there is a burdened family history or when a syndrome is diagnosed for which a genetic etiology has been identified in a clinical population-based study [14].

CNS infections, whether bacterial, viral, parasitic, or fungal, can cause both acute symptomatic seizures and postinfectious epilepsy that manifests months or years later. Infectious epilepsy can develop at any age and can be suspected based on clinical presentation, imaging findings, serologic studies, and knowledge of travel history and endemic exposures. The frequency of seizures among patients with acute infections varies depending on the severity of the disease and the specific infectious agent. Among hospitalized patients with acute bacterial or viral meningoencephalitis, acute symptomatic seizures occur in 15-40% of cases [15]. The central nervous system is often affected by herpes simplex virus, especially in children [16], as well as by such parasites as cysticercaria, onchocerciasis, and malaria plasmodium [17].

Congenital metabolic disorders are a rare but important cause of epilepsy. Although they are classified independently of the genetic and structural etiology of epilepsy, in fact, metabolic disorders leading to epilepsy are often associated with structural abnormalities of the brain and have a clearly defined genetic etiology. Their detection is important for prescribing specific treatment, if any. For example, there are epilepsies associated with glucose transporter type 1 (GLUT-1) deficiency, pyridoxine-dependent epilepsy, glycine encephalopathy (nonketotic hyperglycemia), epilepsy

with cerebral folate deficiency and maple syrup disease [14].

Immunologic causes of epilepsy include autoimmune diseases. Antibody-mediated limbic encephalitis is increasingly being diagnosed as a disease that often causes epilepsy. In addition, several antibodies have been identified that can cause epilepsy, the most common of which are N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDAR), LGI-1 antineuronal nuclear antibody type 1 (ANNA-1), Ma, α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid (AMPA), γ -aminobutyric acid-B (GABA-B), and metabotropic glutamate receptor 5 (mGluR5) [18].

Epilepsy with unknown etiology is becoming less common with improved diagnostic techniques, but about 50% of epilepsy cases still remain without an established etiology, as many patients with epileptic seizures do not have a burdened family history of epilepsy, have normal MRI/CT findings, normal complete metabolic panels, a clinical history that does not correlate with any known genetic syndrome, and no known infectious or autoimmune diseases [19].

There are such concepts as epileptogenesis and epileptic maturation. The former is interpreted as the process that leads to the first spontaneous seizure and repeated epileptiform events after brain damage. The second is defined as secondary changes or progression after epileptogenesis, that is, after the first seizure, up to epileptic status [20].

Epileptogenesis can include various biological pathways and processes, structural and functional changes in nervous tissue [21].

It has been suggested that neurotransmitter signaling pathways are disturbed in epilepsy. Glutamate, the main excitatory neurotransmitter that generates excitatory postsynaptic potentials through neuronal depolarization, acts on ionotropic (AMPA, NMDA, kainate receptor) and metabotropic (G-protein coupled) receptors [22]. The glutamatergic molecular mechanisms involved in the onset and progression of epilepsy include excessive activation of glutamate receptors, increased extracellular glutamate concentration, disruption of glutamatergic transporters, and autoimmune mechanisms [21]. GABA is the main inhibitory neurotransmitter because it generates inhibitory presynaptic potentials by depolarizing neurons. There are 2 types of GABA receptors involved in the pathogenesis of epilepsy: GABA_A and GABA_B. Ionotropic GABA_A receptors provide fast inhibitory presynaptic potentials, G-protein-coupled GABA_B's provide slow ones, regulating the flow of various ions [23]. Reducing GABAergic inhibition can increase the likelihood of generating excitatory postsynaptic potentials and synchronizing spike discharges, and thus induce epileptogenesis. Proposed GABAergic mechanisms include impaired GABA release, changes in GABA receptors, impaired GABA synthesis, and loss of GABAergic neurons [24]. In addition, serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine play a role in epileptogenesis. Neuronal excitability can be reduced by hyperpolarization of glutamatergic neurons via 5-HT_{1A} receptors, depolarization of GABAergic neurons via 5-HT_{2C} receptors, and inhibition of 5-HT₃ and 5-HT₇ receptors [25]. The protective effect of

norepinephrine is explained by counteracting the formation of an epileptic chain and modifying neuronal changes caused by epilepsy [26]. A decrease in inhibitory dopaminergic activity causes a tendency to excessive neuronal excitability and seizures when the corresponding receptors are activated [27].

Channelopathies are key factors in the pathogenesis of human epilepsy, mainly its idiopathic form. Mutations of genes expressing potassium, sodium, chlorine, calcium channels, as well as acetylcholine and GABA receptors, have been reported in idiopathic epilepsy. In addition, channelopathies may also be involved in the pathogenesis of acquired epilepsy due to secondary changes in ion channels through transcriptional and post-translational mechanisms [28].

Impaired hippocampal neurogenesis, the process of neurogeneration and creation of new circuits, has been proposed as another important pathogenetic factor in epilepsy. Various changes include structural, neurochemical, and cellular changes that can occur after acute seizures in patients with brain lesions [29]. Axonal sprouting and synaptogenesis occur in the mossy pathway, and a new neural circuit forms a recurrent excitatory circuit in dentate granule cells, which increases excitability and promotes epileptogenesis [30]. In addition, there is a functional disconnection of basket-like GABAergic (inhibitory) cells from excitatory neurons [31]. These processes involve changes in the functioning of certain neurotropic factors and other hypothalamic proteins [29].

Inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α , have been shown to be produced by microglia and astrocytes in brain regions involved in the generation and propagation of epileptic activity. Their release is accompanied by a cascade of inflammatory responses that can involve neurons and activate the adaptive immune system. At the same time, neuronal apoptosis may also occur, and the blood-brain barrier may be disrupted, and leukocyte penetration into the nervous tissue may increase, which significantly increases nervous excitability and is accompanied by epileptiform brain activity [21].

During epileptogenesis, the overexpression of effector caspases 3 and 6, as well as proteins such as Bcl-2 and Bax, was found in the hippocampus, which may indicate the role of apoptosis in this process [32].

Etiology and Pathogenesis of Metabolic Syndrome

The pathogenesis of MetS is primarily driven by insulin resistance, influenced by lifestyle factors like low physical activity and obesity, as well as genetic predisposition. Hormonal disturbances, particularly involving the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and increased cortisol levels, also play a role. These factors contribute to abdominal obesity, insulin resistance, hypertension, and dyslipidemia, leading to increased risks of type 2 diabetes and atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases [8, 42].

Insulin resistance, a hallmark of MetS, results in impaired glucose uptake and utilization, leading to hyperglycemia. This metabolic disturbance triggers a cascade of compensatory mechanisms, including increased

insulin secretion by the pancreas. Over time, the persistent hyperinsulinemia state can exhaust pancreatic beta cells, leading to the development of type 2 diabetes. Concurrently, insulin resistance affects lipid metabolism, contributing to dyslipidemia characterized by elevated triglycerides and low HDL cholesterol levels [42].

Central obesity, another key component of MetS, is strongly associated with increased visceral fat accumulation. Visceral fat is metabolically active and secretes various adipokines and pro-inflammatory cytokines that contribute to systemic inflammation and insulin resistance. This inflammatory state is further exacerbated by hormonal imbalances, particularly involving the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis. Increased cortisol levels, often resulting from chronic stress or other factors, promote abdominal fat deposition and further insulin resistance [42].

Hypertension, another critical element of MetS, arises from complex interactions between insulin resistance, obesity, and endothelial dysfunction. Insulin resistance impairs nitric oxide-mediated vasodilation, leading to increased vascular resistance and hypertension. Additionally, obesity contributes to increased blood volume and cardiac output, further elevating blood pressure [8].

The complex interplay of environmental, lifestyle, and genetic/epigenetic factors in the pathophysiology of MetS has led to new studies that evaluate new perspectives for early diagnosis, classification of new biomarkers, and identification of potential targets for therapeutic interventions [8].

Fetuin-A, also known as Geremans-Schmid α 2-glycoprotein Geremans-Schmid (GSAG), is a protein with pleiotropic metabolic effects secreted by the liver. In addition to being a hepatokine, fetuin-A has recently been described as a potential adipokine, as its expression and secretion levels have been shown to be increased in the visceral adipose tissue of obese animals and in humans with diabetes mellitus [33]. The association of its circulating levels with MetS is currently gaining importance as a new biomarker and possible risk factor for MetS [34]. Fetuin-A inhibits the tyrosine kinase activity of the insulin receptor, as well as the phosphorylation of IRS-1 and subsequent molecules in the PI3k/akt pathway, and increases the infiltration of adipose tissue by macrophages, which induces the release of proinflammatory cytokines [35].

In addition to their important role in the production of ATP, mitochondria are a major source of reactive oxygen species (ROS) through the leakage of several high-energy electrons from the electron transport chain and their direct reaction with oxygen. However, mitochondria are equipped with a very effective antioxidant mechanism that activates superoxide dismutase and other enzymes to scavenge ROS generated either locally or by other organelles, such as peroxisomes. Thus, mitochondrial dysfunction can lead to excessive ROS formation, which causes cellular damage characteristic of oxidative stress, which contributes to the development of many pathological processes, including MetS [36]. In addition, excessive production of ROS

occurs in MetS: excessive amounts of nutrients in adipocytes induce oxidation of FFAs, which overloads the mitochondrial antioxidant system, and FFAs in adipocytes activate NADPH oxidase [37]. Insulin resistance can also contribute to a decrease in mitochondrial function directly [38]. Reduced energy requirements due to a sedentary lifestyle observed in MetS reduces the level of PGC-1 α (expressed only in response to high energy requirements of the cell) and thus reduces mitochondrial biogenesis. PGC-1 α has been described as an important transcriptional activator and a master regulator of mitochondrial biogenesis and function, including oxidative phosphorylation and ROS detoxification [39].

Dysregulation of circulating microRNA expression has been shown to be associated with various components of MetS. For example, miR-17-5p and miR-519d are associated with obesity and lipogenesis, miR-375 controls insulin secretion from the pancreas, and the let-7 family affects insulin sensitivity and regulates various stages of glucose metabolism. In addition, differential expression of microRNAs between the sexes has been reported, which may help explain the sex differences associated with the progression of MetS and its complications [40].

Association Between Epilepsy and Metabolic Syndrome

Obesity and MetS are frequently observed in patients with epilepsy (PE). Obesity and MetS affect not only the physical fitness and quality of life of these patients, but also adherence to antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) and seizure control [41]. Obesity leads to a state of chronic inflammation in the body, as excess adipose tissue increases the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, inflammatory markers, including IL-6, IL-8, TNF, and CRP. Clinical and animal studies have shown an important role of inflammation in the development and progression of epilepsy. Inflammation disrupts the neural circuits that control the lack of satiation, which leads to further disturbances in lipid metabolism, and this closes the “vicious circle”. Neuroimaging studies have shown that obesity is accompanied by focal structural changes in many brain regions. A large 8-year prospective study found a link between overweight and hippocampal atrophy, which is a component of the pathogenesis of pharmacoresistant epilepsy. The distribution of adipose tissue in the body in obesity is also important: increased hip circumference increases the risk of developing juvenile myoclonic epilepsy and epilepsy in general, and high BMI increases the risk of developing childhood absence epilepsy [43, 44, 45].

Both direct and indirect links between hypertension and the development of epilepsy have been reliably established. The direct link is mainly provided by excessive activation of the renin-angiotensin system (RAS), which is confirmed by the delay of seizures and a decrease in their frequency with the use of AT1 receptor antagonists. Angiotensin is believed to act as a neurotransmitter or neuromodulator in certain cerebral pathways, either by directly affecting specific receptors or by interacting closely with dopaminergic and GABAergic systems. An indirect connection is established in several ways. Stroke-related seizures: acute symptomatic seizures and post-stroke epilepsy (PSE). Acute

symptomatic seizures are a consequence of acute ischemic injury, which leads to glutamate excitotoxicity with accumulation of intracellular calcium, transmembrane depolarization, and a decrease in the seizure threshold. The pathophysiology of PSE is based on hyperexcitability and hypersynchrony of neurons, secondary changes in membrane properties, deafferentation, selective neuronal loss, and collateral branching. Seizures associated with small vessel disease (SVD): Possible pathogenetic mechanisms may include the presence of cortical microinfarcts, as well as the effects of cortical deafferentation due to white matter damage in surrounding or distant areas. In addition, both SVD and epilepsy may develop as part of a common neurodegenerative process that remains to be elucidated. Seizures associated with posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES): PRES can develop in acute hypertension because of BBB dysfunction, increased vascular permeability and edema. It often occurs in patients with eclampsia, which manifests itself during pregnancy or after childbirth with hypertension, proteinuria, peripheral edema, and epileptic seizures [46, 47, 48, 49].

There is a definite link between hyperglycemia and the development of epilepsy. Hyperglycemia can lead to changes in brain function, including changes in electrical activity, which can provoke epileptic seizures in patients with epilepsy. Hyperglycemia may result in hyperactivation of NMDA receptors in the brain. Hyperglycemia is also associated with water and electrolyte disorders, namely hyponatremia, hypercalcemia, and hyperosmolarity of blood plasma. Hypercalcemia may occur because of insulin resistance/deficiency-induced hyperparathyroidism. It can cause seizures due to induction of vasoconstriction and hypertensive encephalopathy. Glucose enhances synaptic transmission, which leads to greater neuronal excitability, possibly due to its action on ATP-sensitive potassium channels. Hyperglycemia causes damage to cerebral blood vessels, which also causes epileptic seizures due to focal cerebral ischemia. Chronic diabetic hyperglycemia, defined by elevated HbA1c levels, correlates with higher BBB permeability and accumulation of glycosylation end products in the brain. Fluctuations in glucose levels induce oxidative stress more significantly than sustained high glucose levels [50, 51, 52, 53].

The development of the metabolic syndrome is influenced by the manifestations and methods of epilepsy control. Obesity and MetS are often observed in more than half of patients with epilepsy. They affect not only the physical fitness and quality of life of these patients, but also compliance with antiepileptic medication and seizure control. This may be a result of metabolic disorders associated with seizures, prolonged use of antiepileptic drugs and a high level of sedentary lifestyle, as well as other behavioral risk factors in the epilepsy population. Certain antiepileptic drugs, such as carbamazepine and phenytoin, are known to alter the metabolic profile of a person, particularly the lipid profile, the profile of coagulation factors and acute phase proteins. Some antiepileptic drugs cause insulin resistance. The increased risk of developing MetS in people with epilepsy may also be associated with a decrease in quality

of life with reduced mental functions and the presence of psychoemotional stress. Patients with epilepsy have a significantly lower life expectancy and 2-3 times higher mortality compared to the general population, with a mortality rate of 40-50% from CVD diseases [54, 55, 56, 57].

Conclusion

There is a stable association of such components of the metabolic syndrome as hypertension, obesity, and hyperglycemia with epilepsy, but the mechanisms of this association are not yet fully understood. A link has been established between the manifestations and methods of epilepsy control and the development of metabolic syndrome. It is necessary to establish a clear cause-and-effect relationship of the metabolic syndrome as a direct risk factor for epilepsy, which requires a more in-depth study of the pathogenesis of both conditions and elucidation of the mechanisms of the complex effect of the components of the metabolic syndrome on the processes of epileptogenesis.

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